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EVALUATING THE SOCIO-ECONOMIC ASPECTS OF PUBLIC SERVICES IN RAILWAY PASSENGER TRANSPORT

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INTRODUCTION

Passenger services operated under the public interest form the majority of performances on the EU railway transport market. Alongside the questions about the quality of services and the final price of this product for passengers, there are also significant effects from the social point of view. We can divide these social effects depending on whether they influence the public sector, railway undertakings or passengers and society. As the segment of PSO in passenger rail transport is subsidized, it is also very sensitive to the current political situation in the country and a set system of allocation of public spending. The situation across the EU Member states is not uniform and authorities are groping in the ideal setting of conditions for the selection of railway undertakings.

The nature of most rail passenger transport services, especially regional and suburban, requires subsidies from the state or regional authorities. Public service obligation (PSO) are such services, that the railway undertaking would not otherwise provide due to their inefficiency or would not provide them to sufficient extent necessary to ensure the basic transport package (ec.europa.eu, 2022). These services are usually provided based on a contract. Public service obligation (PSO) is in general defined as a public contract concluded between the ordering authority and the railway undertaking (RU), in which the RU undertakes to operate the public services in railway passenger transport based on this contract and the ordering authority is obligated to provide the compensation (usually in the form of a financial subsidy) for these services. This compensation can be calculated as a difference between the economically justified costs and the revenues of railway undertaking from the provision of these services, depending on the type of contract and revenue-risk distribution. Conclusion of the contracts must be in accordance with the Regulation of the European Parliament and of the Council No 1370/2007 of 23 October 2007 on public passenger transport services by rail and by road. This legal document deals with the basic conditions of PSO contracts, the maximum duration of the contract, with the ways of contracting PSO in railway transport and with the methodology of the compensation.

In this paper, an evaluation of existing public contracts in post-soviet countries which are now Members States of the European Union is performed, with an emphasis on the determination of social costs and benefits for all subjects of the PSO contracts (contracting authority and railway undertaking). The resulting model includes key aspects of each subject in the PSO contracting process and synergic effects between them from the socio-economic point of view. Based on these results, an optimal model for concluding the public service contracts can be determined in future. This model can be used for making the decision, which model of contracting PSO should be used in specific conditions to reach the optimal benefits from the synergy effects and increase the efficiency of PSO. The paper also consists of the discussion on results and the possibilities for further research in this area.

1. THEORETICAL BACKGROUND

1.1. LITERATURE REVIEW

The issue of PSO contracting in passenger railway transport is a relatively current and unexplored topic, which was dealt with by only a small number of authors. In the available literature, however, we can still find several studies focused on public service obligations. Poliak et. al (2018) identified the importance of public passenger transport and define public competition as an effective method to increase its competitiveness. The study deals primarily with the awarding of PSO contracts in road passenger transport. The same issue is addressed by Valkama et al (2018) and Iossa and Waterson (2019), while examining the impact of this sector of public passenger transport on costs, economic efficiency, and quality of services. The PSO segment in regional rail transport have been addressed by Wegelin and von Arx (2016), namely the solution of the transaction costs of different forms of management by comparing the German model of competitive PSO contract awarding with the Swiss direct model of awarding contracts. Nash and Smith (2020) examined the procurement of public passenger transport in Great Britain in the road and rail sector. Crossmann and Mouse (2015) dealt with the issue of financing rail transport in the form of subsidies and the question of whether these subsidies are determined by the conditions of the given sector or leave room for the preferences of individual governments. In his work, Guillen (2022) summarized new challenges for future PSO contracts in railway transport. He focused on the legislative side of public tenders and their impact on the process of railway liberalization in the European Union. The evaluation of PSO from the point of view of their financing, either by self-governing bodies or the railway company, using an integrated dynamic fuzzy approach (fuzzy EDAS model) was dealt with by Veskovic et al. (2020). Their model was built for various cost-benefit situations, such as reduction of operating costs, increase in fare revenue, and their combinations, and was subsequently tested in the real conditions of a railway undertaking operating passenger transport.

In the available scientific studies, the issue of PSO contracts in the air transport and energy sector is primarily addressed. Kinene et al. (2022) addressed the issue of air carriers' access to public tenders for the operation of subsidized airlines from a legislative point of view. where they created a new approach based on streamlining the carrier selection process. The approach using Data envelopment analysis (DEA) analysis for calculating the efficiency of production units was used to evaluate the efficiency of PSO in air transport by Costa et al. (2021). The results of their study identify air carriers according to performance, as well as routes within Europe where airlines tend to achieve higher or lower efficiency values. PSOs in the field of energy in the context of energy sustainability and security were the topic of a paper by Karpavicius & Balezentis (2021).

1.2. MODELS OF PSO CONTRACTING IN RAILWAY TRANSPORT

Conclusion of the PSO contract is a complex process requiring the cooperation between ordering authorities and railway undertakings. In general, there are two main ways, how to conclude these contracts from the legal perspective. They differ in the transparency of the process, its speed and the requirements placed on railway undertakings, as well as in the participation of RUs in this process and selection of final railway carrier for the contract. These two basic models of concluding PSO are:

- direct awarding,
- public tendering.

Direct awarding and public tendering

By direct award, the contracting authority (state or regional) usually conducts an internal negotiation with railway undertaking whose technical base meet the required range of services. The contracting parties shall subsequently agree on the range of services and the amount of compensation (figure 1). The contract is usually signed for the period of 5 – 10 years. This model is still used by most of contracting authorities across the European countries as the main method of selection of the railway undertaking for PSO contract, especially in the post-soviet countries which are now members of the European Union (Slovakia, Poland, Hungary, Czech Republic, Baltic, and Balkan states).

Figure 1: Direct awarding of PSO services (methodology). Source: Domeny et al. (2022)

Public tendering is a process of non-discriminatory and transparent selection of railway undertaking, which will provide services in a certain area based on the order from the competent authority. Public tender is accessible for every RU which meet the conditions set out in the tender announcement. The successful railway undertaking is usually the one who offers the lowest required subsidy per unit of performance. The main advantage of public tenders by their

planned implementation was an increase in the quality of services and a reduction in the amount of compensation paid from the public budget (Regulation of the EU No 2016/2338, 2016).

The implementation of public tenders, especially in the countries of Eastern Europe, encounters various barriers. These tenders often ended without a successful tenderer. Tenders require well-developed tender conditions as well as sufficient time for their fulfilling after the contract has been awarded. The mechanism of public tenders is shown in detail on figure 2. The first steps are a tender announcement and publication of tender documents by ordering authority. In these tender documents, main requirements on the range of public services, their quality and definition of economically justified costs are published. In the next step, tender offers are submitted by individual railway undertakings, followed by their transparent evaluation, a determination of the winner and the act of agreeing on the final terms before signing the contract (Domeny et al., 2022).

Figure 2: Public tendering of PSO services (methodology). Source: Domeny et al. (2022)

Direct award and public tendering are two basic models of concluding PSO contracts. In addition to these two, a model of so-called market consultation is applied in some countries, especially in the Czech Republic. The approaching end of the contractual period of PSO contracts and short time for preparing and conducting the entire tender process meant that the contracting authority (Ministry of transport for long-distance services and self-governing regions for regional services) had to find solutions to speed up this process and at the same time increase the quality of passenger services and open the national market for competition. They modified the direct award by implementing it in the form of a “market consultations”, where individual railway undertakings submit their offers and the required amount of compensation, while the contracting authority decides on the most advantageous offer based on the selected criteria (Figure 3). Subsequently, negotiations will take place with the selected railway undertaking, which lead to the conclusion of a contract. The main advantage of this model is the shorter duration of the process, the possibility of choosing the most effective offer and the impossibility of challenging the proceedings with the antitrust authority. Its disadvantage is the fact that the customer can only count on those railway companies that already have a sufficiently large rolling stock and staff or can ensure it in short time period (Domeny et al., 2022).

Figure 3: Market consultation for PSO services (methodology). Source: Source: Domeny et al. (2022)

Across the EU countries, there is still strong predominance of direct award in PSO contracting. Table 1 summarize models used by public authorities in each of Member States. In the case of countries that also applied public tenders, it was mainly for regional and suburban transport services, except for the Czech Republic, which successfully allocated services based on public tenders also in the case of some long-distance transport lines ordered centrally from the state authority. Public tenders for regional services are common mainly in Germany and Sweden, which were also the first that had applied them in practice in the late 90's, followed by the Netherlands and Denmark.

Table 1: Overview of PSO contracting models across the EU Member States

Country	Model of PSO contracting
Belgium	direct award
Bulgaria	direct award
Czechia	direct award, public tender, market consultation
Denmark	direct award, public tender
Estonia	direct award
Finland	direct award
France	direct award
Greece	direct award
The Netherlands	direct award, public tender
Croatia	direct award
Ireland	direct award
Lithuania	direct award
Latvia	direct award
Luxemburg	direct award
Hungary	direct award
Germany	public tender, direct award
Poland	direct award
Portugal	direct award
Austria	direct award
Romania	direct award
Slovakia	direct award, market consultation
Slovenia	direct award
Spain	direct award
Sweden	public tender
Italy	direct award, public tender

Source: author by Independent Regulators' Group – Rail (2022), Špětik (2022), CER (2017)

Revenue risk in PSO contracts

Based on the contract, revenue from fares may accrue to the ordering authority or to the railway company itself. Their recipient then also bears the risk of their changes and fluctuations. Based on the responsibility for revenue risk, we divide PSO contracts into two groups:

- net – railway undertaking bears the responsibility for revenue risk,
- gross – ordering authority of PSO bears the responsibility for revenue risk and paid to railway undertaking only the difference between economically justified costs and revenues from fares.

The advantage of gross contracts is that the ordering authority pays the railway undertaking only the actual amount of compensation. In this case, however, the RU is not motivated to minimize costs and it is more advantageous for him to generate minimum sales at high costs (Jarošincová, 2015). In the case of net contracts, the railway undertaking is paid the compensation agreed in the contract regardless of its actual costs and sales, which motivates the RU to optimize the costs of operating these services. In this case, the risk for the ordering authority is excessive compensation, which he is forced to pay if the railway undertaking has maximized its profit (Jarošincová, 2015).

1.3. AIM, PURPOSE, OBJECTIVE

The main aim of this paper is to identify the mutual relationships between all subjects on the PSO rail passenger market, and subsequently propose the synergy model considering all socio-economics aspects of PSO contracts from the perspective of contracting authority, railway undertaking and passengers.

Main research question according to the aim of this study was: What are the synergic effects of socio-economic aspects of public services in passenger rail transport under public obligation. Synergy model in general describes the main relationships between all subjects and their mutual influences. A detailed analysis of the existing PSO contracts would help us to find out more about the inputs usable in the final construction of the model.

The final output of the synergy model will be presented graphically with all important links and relationships market, as it can be easier to understand for all professional subjects and for general public.

2. METHODOLOGY AND DATA

In this chapter, the methodology used for the determination of socio-economics aspects of public services in passenger railway transport will be described. Subsequently, data about the PSO contracts in post-soviet EU member countries are collected and analysed, for the purpose of final synergy model composition.

2.1. METHODOLOGY

The first step in the model composition process is the definition of the sample, which is formed by existing PSO contracts in so-called Visegrad 4 countries (Slovakia, Czechia, Poland, and Hungary). Each of the examined country was characterized by different approach to PSO contract conclusion, which is across the EU Member States unique and therefore they have been selected for the purpose of our study. After studying and comparing these PSO, we can determine the key factors and characteristics of public services in passenger rail transport for the subsequent detailed analysis. Is it important to look at these factors in the light of each other from the perspective of public authorities responsible for contracting PSO, railway undertakings (carriers) operating these services and passengers as a final user of public transport services. By this approach it is possible to look deeper into relationships between all subjects on the railway market with public services and find possible synergy effects from the socio-economics point of view. That means to determine the service and financial flows, flows of social and transactional costs and the degree of their mutual influence.

Figure 4: Methodology of research. Source: author

2.2. INPUT DATA

Table 2 shows the main differences and characteristics of PSO contracts in these countries. Slovakia and Hungary apply central system of PSO conclusion, where all services are under responsibility of the central state authority, usually the Ministry of transport or infrastructure. In Czech Republic and Poland, we can see different approach, where long-distance services are contracted by the central authority and regional services belong under the responsibility of regional authorities.

Table 2: Differences in PSO contract conclusion across V-4 countries

Country	Long-distance PSO	Regional PSO	Way of contracting
Slovakia	central	central	direct award, market consultation
Czech Republic	central	local	direct award, market consultation, public tender
Poland	central	local	direct award
Hungary	central	central	direct award

Source: author by Independent Regulators' Group – Rail (2022), Špětik (2022), CER (2017)

All the data have been collected from the existing PSO contracts using the available reports published by contracting authorities and requesting them, if these data were missing or incomplete. The sample consists of:

- Slovakia: 1 PSO contract for all services between The Ministry of Transport and national carrier ZSSK (from December 2023 one additional contract with private carrier Leo Express for regional services on individual route),
- Czech Republic: PSO contracts for long-distance services concluded by the Ministry of Transport and PSO contracts for regional services concluded by 14 individual regional authorities or integrated transport system coordinators,
- Poland: 2 PSO contracts for long-distance services (separately domestic and international) between the Ministry of Infrastructure and national carrier PKP IC, and PSO contracts for regional services concluded between 16 individual regional authorities and national carrier Polregio or railway undertakings owned by the region itself,
- Hungary: 1 PSO contract for all services between The Ministry of Transport and national carriers MÁV-Start and Gysev.

As we can see, there also is a big difference in the number of contracts between examined countries. Some of them apply separate PSO contracts with national carrier for domestic and international services in long-distance transport, another like Czech Republic have concluded

contracts for these services with several carriers including the private (Regio Jet, Arriva and GW Train regio), but most of them are still under the operation of national carrier České dráhy (ČD). In the field of regional railway transport is common that responsible authorities on the regional level in Czech Republic and Poland concluded more than one contract with the same or different carriers, according to individual “operating files” created based on the territory, rolling stock used or traction. In Slovakia and Hungary are all PSO services under one big contract without distinguishing the nature or scope of these services, which can be at some point problematic, especially because this approach is not considering different capacity of railway vehicles or character of services (long distance / regional).

PSO contracts - Slovakia

The current system of PSO services in Slovakia is characterized by the central ordering of all services (long-distance and regional) in railway passenger transport by the state authority, which is the Ministry of Transport of the Slovak Republic. During the period until 2022, all contracts were awarded exclusively by direct award, usually to the incumbent ZSSK, a.s. In 2012, a direct awarded contract was also concluded with the Czech private railway company Regio Jet, for the provision of services on regional route between Bratislava, Dunajská Streda and Komárno. On this line, following a transitional period ensured by the incumbent in cooperation with the Austrian Federal Railways, the ordering authority decided to select a railway company for the next 10-year period through a market consultation system, known primarily from the Czech Republic. Subsequently, a contract was concluded with the Czech private carrier Leo Express Tenders, while the start of operations is expected from December 2023. In the case of the share of revenue from fares, there was a sharp decrease after 2014, when free transportation was introduced for selected groups of passengers, and thus the amount of compensation paid to the customer increased. The current PSO contract was concluded in 2021 for a period of 10 years, but with the assumption of the gradual exclusion of part of the services and the conclusion of a new contract based on a public tender (Ministry of Transport of the Slovak republic, 2022).

The financial model used for compensation payments consists of individual groups of payment parameters:

- cost reimbursement parameter depending on the number and type of vehicles (investment costs, vehicle rental),
- cost reimbursement parameter depending on performance km and type of vehicle operated (material costs and labor costs, vehicle maintenance, spare parts, vehicle operation),
- parameter of reimbursement of costs depending on hours of performance and type of personnel (primarily personal costs in operation),

- parameter of reimbursement of costs depending on the weight of the train and km of performance (diesel, traction energy),
- selected costs,
- other cost reimbursement parameter (overhead and other costs),
- parameter of payment of reasonable profit (Ministry of Transport of the Slovak republic, 2022).

There have been several public tenders in Slovakia, but they all ended in failure due to non-fulfilment of the public tender documents conditions by the railway undertakings or submitting an offer with higher value than expected one by the Ministry of Transport. Overview of these public tenders providing basic information about them is presented in Table 3. Only one successful “tender” was in year 2021, when the Ministry decided to conclude PSO contract on the route Bratislava – Komárno using direct award with previous market consultations with railway undertakings and choosing the best offer according to the amount of the contract and minimum quality requirements.

Table 3: Overview of public tenders in Slovakia

Public tender	Year of announcement	Time period of operation	Number of participants	Successful participant	Final amount of contract
Žilina – Rajec	2018	10 years	1 (incumbent)	none	-
Košice – Moldava and Bodvou	2018	10 years	rejected before offers submission		
Bratislava – Komárno	2018	10 years	1 (Regio Jet)	none	-
Bratislava – Komárno	2020	10 years	1 (incumbent)	none	-
Žilina – Rajec	2020	10 years	0	rejected due to zero participants	
Bratislava – Komárno (market consultation)	2021	10 years (from 2023)	3 (ZSSK, Leo Express, Yosaria Trains)	Leo Express	111,796 mil. EUR (11,89 EUR/train-km)

Source: author by Ministry of Transport of the Slovak republic (2022)

PSO contracts - Czech Republic

Ordering of PSO in the Czech Republic takes place in parallel at two levels. The first is the central level, under which international and long-distance transport falls (except for open access services on the main route Praha - Ostrava), whose customer is the Ministry of Transport of the Czech Republic. The ordering of regional PSO takes place at the level of 14 self-governing units (regions). In the case of PSO crossing the territory of several self-governing regions, contracts are concluded either by one or based on the cooperation of several regions.

Table 4 presents an overview of individual PSO ordering authorities in the Czech Republic, including the current number of concluded contracts and the used methods of ordering these services. Exclusive direct award (usually to the incumbent) is still used in 6 self-governing regions, while other regions and the Ministry of Transport have also switched to a system of direct assignment through market consultations with railway undertakings. As a rule, the same territorial units also have experience in organizing public tenders, while in the South Moravian region PSOs were ordered based on a public tender for the territory of the entire region (due to the resulting requirements for vehicles and personnel, the incumbent was the only participant in this tender).

Table 4: Overview of PSO in Czech Republic

Ordering authority	Number of contracts	Way of contracting	Revenue risk	Private carriers
Ministry of Transport	10	direct award, public tender, market consultation	net	yes
South-moravian region	1	public tender	gross	ni
Olomouc region	3	direct award, public tender	gross	no
Zlín region	4	direct award, market consultation	gross	yes
Plzeň region	2	direct award, public tender	gross	yes
Ústí region	11	direct award, market consultation	gross	yes
Liberec region	9	direct award, market consultation	gross	yes
Hradec Králové region	3	direct award	net	yes
Karlovy Vary region	2	direct award	net	yes
region Vysočina	2	direct award	net	yes
Moravian-silesian region	8	direct award	net	yes
South-bohemian kraj	5	direct award, public tender	net	yes
Central-bohemian region	3	direct award	net	yes

Capital city of Praha	5	direct award	net	yes
Pardubice region	2	direct award, market consultation	net	yes

Source: author by Ministry of Transport of Czech Republic (2022) smlouvy.gov.cz (2022)

From the perspective of revenue risk, the contracts concluded by the central authority for long-distance transport services are in the net mode, while the individual regions gradually switch to the gross mode for regional contracts (currently the Olomouc, Zlín, Plzeň, Ústí and Liberec regions), which they see the advantage mainly in the simpler process of establishing and adjusting uniform tariff conditions for contracts concluded with different carriers. Most of the ordering authorities currently have contracts with private railway undertakings, either in the form of direct award (e.g. Central-bohemian region), market consultations (e.g. Zlín, Pardubice, Ústí, Liberec region) or public tender (South-bohemian region).

PSO contracts – Poland

The method of concluding PSO contracts from a territorial point of view in Poland is analogous to the system used in the Czech Republic. The central authority, which is the Ministry of Infrastructure, is responsible for ordering long-distance transport services (except services in the open access mode), which currently has two PSO contracts with the incumbent PKP IC (for domestic long-distance and international transport). The responsibility for concluding contracts in regional transport is transferred to self-governing units, which in the case of Poland are 16 Voivodeships. There is currently a strong predominance of direct awarding of PSO contracts in Poland. Table 5 presents the overview of PSO contracts concluded by Polish ordering authorities.

Table 5: Overview of PSO in Poland

Ordering authority	Number of contracts	Way of contracting	Private carriers
Lubuskie voivodeship	3	direct award	yes
Wielkopolskie voivodeship	2	direct award	yes
Podkarpackie voivodeship	1	direct award	no
Łódz voivodeship	3	direct award	yes
Zachodniopomorskie voivodeship	1	direct award	no
Dolnoslaskie voivodeship	2	direct award	yes
Ministry of Infrastructure	2	direct award	no
Mazowi voivodeship	2	direct award	yes
Warmińsko-Mazurskie voivodeship	1	direct award	no

świętokrzyskie voivodeship	1	direct award	no
Malopolskie voivodeship	3	direct award	yes
Podlaskie voivodeship	1	direct award	no
Lubelskie voivodeship	1	direct award	no
Opolskie voivodeship	1	direct award	no
Pomorskie voivodeship	2	direct award	yes
Slaskie voivodeship	2	direct award	yes
Kujawsko-pomorskie voivodeship	2	direct award	yes

Source: author by bip.gov.pl (2022)

However, the Polish model is specific in that some voivodeships outsource these services to their own railway undertakings, which were established by them and are their majority shareholder. This happened as a result of dissatisfaction with the price and level of service provided by the incumbent for regional transport Polregio (formerly Przewozy regionalne). We can find such regional carriers in most voivodeships. From the point of view of revenue risk, these are gross contracts, when the railway company is paid the difference between economically justified costs and revenue from the provision of services.

PSO contracts – Hungary

In Hungary, there are two PSO contracts inclusive of all services (both long-distance and regional), divided into two national incumbents, which are MÁV-Start and Gysev in the Hungarian-Austrian borderland. Contracts are concluded from central transport authority by direct award, usually for the time period of 10 years. Hungary is in general known as a country with several barriers and issues for entering the railway market in comparison with other EU Member States, such as prioritization of national railway undertakings by the government and vertically integrated model with infrastructure manager and carrier form part of same holding company.

Indicators of existing contracts

By examining the existing PSO contracts in V-4 countries an overview was made of indicators, or factors, which are part of the contract conditions. They differ based on the country and individual contracting authority, but in general they have these points in common:

- parties of contract,
- validity period of the contract,
- area serviced (routes or lines),

- contracted volume of operational performance per year during the duration of the contract,
- methodology of the compensation calculation,
- expected amount of compensation per year during the duration of the contract,
- expected amount of compensation per performance unit,
- method of the compensation payment,
- general terms and conditions.

The main difference between individual contracts is defined by the number of annexes of the contract, in which other requirements of the contracting authority are specified, e.g. in the field of:

- rolling stock requirements – age, traction, capacity, and other technical specification of vehicles used for PSO (AC, toilets, access for disabled person, noise level, energy consumption, emissions...),
- expected timetable – some contracting authorities, especially by using the public tender for PSO contract conclusion, submit a draft timetable for the specific route in the tender documents, including the requirements on circulation of vehicles and staff,
- quality requirements – related especially to the accuracy and timeliness of operated services, expressed as a percentage of the desired level of accuracy and timeliness,
- revenue risk in the contract,
- financial model – a methodology for determination of economically justified costs and expected revenues related to specific PSO contract,
- tariff conditions and fares – use and specification of regulated fares for PSO operated under the contract and recognition of tariff conditions issued by another authority.

3. RESULTS

Main result of this study is a construction of the synergy model of socio-economics aspects of public services in passenger railway transport, taking into account different perspectives of the contracting authorities, railway undertakings and passengers. This model created using the previous analysis of PSO contracts and their indicators form a basis for the further evaluation of efficiency of public services in passenger railway transport.

3.1. KEY PSO INDICATORS

From the perspective of socio-economical influence on the railway passenger services, several important indicators of PSO contracts were considered, which we focused in the research and used for the final model creation. We summarized these indicators, resulting from the content of specific PSO contracts, from the perspective of contracting authority, railway carrier and passenger in Table 6.

Table 6: Matrix of input indicators of PSO contracts from perspectives of main PSO market subjects

Contracting authority	Railway carrier	Passenger
Way of contracting [binomial]	Time period of the contract [years]	Quality requirements (rolling stocks, regularity...)
Character of services [binomial]	Operational performance of railway services [train-km]	Timeliness and accuracy requirements
Time period of the contract [years]	Operational performance of railway services [seat-km]	Amount of regulated fare
Operational performance of railway services [train-km]	Way of compensation payment [binomial]	
Operational performance of railway services [seat-km]	Agreed amount of the compensation for PSO [EUR]	
Way of compensation payment [binomial]	Timetable requirements	
Agreed amount of the compensation for PSO [EUR]	Rolling stock requirements	
Compensation per performance unit [EUR/km, EUR/seat]	Quality requirements	

Timetable requirements	Timeliness and accuracy requirements	
Rolling stock requirements		
Transactional costs of the contract conclusion process [EUR]		
Opportunity costs saving [EUR]		

Source: author

The main difference between these three perspectives of the contracting authority, railway undertaking, and passengers is how the participants on the railway passenger market view on PSO contracts and what they prefer during the negotiations of the contracts. For the contracting authority are the most important factors regarding to the time period of contract, way of concluding the contract and mainly the agreed amount of the compensation for these services, which will be paid to the railway undertaking. Carriers have to take into account especially the rolling stock, quality of services and timeliness and accuracy requirements of the contracting authority, based on which they decide when choosing a railway undertaking for PSO. Passengers are looking on the resulting process, which is the operation of PSO in sufficient quality, regularity and for acceptable price.

We looked on the indicators from all three perspectives in selected PSO contracts in Slovakia, Czechia and Poland to evaluate and subsequently compare them based on quantitative and qualitative criteria. First, we compare in Table 7 contracts with bigger range of services, concluded generally by the central authority.

Table 7: Comparison of indicators of centrally concluded PSO contracts

Indicator/PSO contract	Slovakia Ministry of Transport and ZSSK	Czech Republic Ministry of Transport and ČD (Ex2 + R18)	Czech Republic Ministry of Transport and Regiojet (R8)
Way of contracting	Direct award	Direct award	Public tender
Character of services	Long-distance and regional	Long-distance	Long-distance
Time period of contract	10 years	10 years	8 years
Operational performance	35 mil. train-km/year	4,4 mil. train-km/year	2,1 mil. train-km/year
Amount of compensation	503 mil. EUR/year	18,9 mil. EUR/year	10,5 mil. EUR/year
Compensation per performance unit	14,37 EUR/train-km	4,3 EUR/train-km	5 EUR/train-km

Timetable requirements	Not defined in contract	Defined timetable of trains on all lines	Defined timetable of trains on the line
Rolling stock requirements	Not defined in contract	Capacity requirements according to individual trains (including first class)	Capacity requirements according to individual trains (including first class)
Quality requirements	Defined for selected trains (express trains on route Bratislava – Košice)	Accessibility of trains for disabled person, hot food on board, 230V plugs	Accessibility of trains for disabled person, 230V plugs, Wi-fi access, snacks on board
Timeliness and accuracy requirements	Timeliness – 98 % required Accuracy – 98,3 % required	90 % accuracy level of trains required	90 % accuracy level of trains required

Source: author by Ministry of Transport of the Slovak Republic (2022), Ministry of Transport of the Czech Republic (2022)

As we can see, the period of contract is mostly longer for these type of services (up to 10 years which is the maximum by using the direct award for the contract conclusion). The range of services and operational performance under these central PSO depends on the territory for which the contract is concluded. In Czech Republic there is a one “big” contract for the whole network and other contracts (as in Table 7) for the specified long-distance lines, especially excluded from the big contract due to public tendering or nature of services (Ex 2 and R18 are the most important and profitable lines in the country, on the route between Praha and Olomouc). For the timetable requirements, it is common that tendered contracts have a defined timetable. The big contract in Slovakia defines only range of services on individual routes, but the time positions of trains are specified by the ordering authority in cooperation with the railway undertaking after the contract conclusion, annually during the timetable composition. They are also significant differences between the quality requirements for PSO in individual countries. In Slovakia, they are requirements for the capacity and technical specifications of vehicles valid only for express trains on the main route between Bratislava and Košice. Czech Republic contract authorities usually define detailed requirements for each route, like accessibility of trains for disabled, food or snacks on the board and accessibility of plugs for electronic devices charging.

The next comparison in Table 8 is focused on the regional services, which are contracted by the local authorities mostly in Czech Republic and Poland. In case of Czechia, we have chosen one contract concluded with private railway undertaking and second one with the incumbent. In

Poland we decided to analyse a contract concluded with regional-owned railway undertaking, which is very common for regional services in this country.

Table 8: Comparison of indicators of local concluded PSO contracts

Indicator/PSO contract	Czech Republic Region Zlín and Arriva vlaky	Czech Republic South Bohemian region and České dráhy	Poland Malopolski region and Koleje Malopolskie
Way of contracting	Market consultation	Direct award	Direct award
Character of services	Regional	Regional – electric traction	Regional
Time period of contract	10 years	10 years	10 years
Operational performance	1,87 mil. train-km/year	3,05 mil. train-km/year	2,55 mil. train-km/year
Amount of compensation	Defined only for the performance unit	19,2 mil. EUR/year	12,5 mil. EUR/year
Compensation per performance unit	6,98 EUR/train-km	4,16 EUR/train-km	Not defined in contract, only total amount
Timetable requirements	Defined timetable of trains on all lines	Defined trains with route and range of operational performance	
Rolling stock requirements	Specific vehicles defined in contract	Capacity requirements according to individual routes	Specific vehicles are not defined
Quality requirements	According to operating vehicles	Minimum Capacity of vehicles, maximum speed, accessibility for disabled, information system for passengers	Heating and air conditioning in vehicles, functional door, requirements on toilets equipment
Timeliness and accuracy requirements	Timeliness – 99,5 % required Accuracy – 90 % required	Accuracy – 95 % required	Accuracy – 90 % required

Source: author by smlouvy.gov.cz (2022) and bip.gov.pl (2022)

Looking on the indicators of these three PSO contracts for regional services, we can see that the range of operational performance and amount of compensation is much lower. Some contracts define both the annual compensation and compensation per performance unit (usually per train-km), some of them determine only one. In case of Czech Republic contracts, a detailed financial model is attached, containing of individual costs and revenues items and detailed methodology of calculation of the compensation amount. The most significant differences we can find in rolling stock and quality requirements, which are in general less detailed than in case of central contracts for long-distance services. There is only small number of contracts which define specific vehicles for the operation of services, mainly the public tendered PSO in Czech Republic. It is common that only capacity requirements and general requirements on vehicles (e.g. toilets, functional doors and heating) were agreed in the regional PSO contracts.

3.2. SYNERGY MODEL

The conditions of individual contracts vary even within the PSO falling under one contracting authority, which open the space for the simplification and unification. To evaluate and subsequently determine the optimal model of the contract conditions, it is necessary to consider all socio-economics aspects of PSO, because these services have strong influence on the public sector and public spending in the form of subsidies. Not only one aspect can be assigned exclusively to the one of these subjects but have a significant impact on each of them. It is important first to know all relationships between these market subjects and how they can influence each other. Main advantage of the synergy model is its ability to help by determining a complex model for evaluating PSO services and contracts (e.g. DEA efficiency or multi-criteria approach). In practice, it can guide contracting authorities and carriers in concluding new PSO contracts, so that they are advantageous for both parties and ultimately bring benefits for passengers. On the other side, the synergy model is only a supporting approach with a recommendatory character, and in this case, it is created in the specific conditions of specific countries.

Determination of key mutual relationships

The general flow between all three main subjects on the PSO market is characterized as a movement of services contracted by the public authority, provided by the railway undertaking (career), and used by the passengers. And the other side, there is a financial flow from passengers to careers as a fare payment, and from the contracting authority to railway undertaking in the form of the compensation of provable loss (Figure 5). For all subjects, there is also an in-house flow of transactional and administrative costs related to the PSO provision. Is it significant especially inside the public authority responsible for contracting PSO, due to specificity and time and personal demands of the contracting process.

Figure 5: General flows between subjects on the PSO market. Source: author

Based on the analysis of the contracts and its annexes in selected countries, we have defined mutual relationships between the market subjects for each of the key indicators of PSO contracts:

- Character of services → for the relationship between contracting authority and carrier represents mainly the scope of the services contracted (operated), according to the increasing operational performance due to longer lines of long-distance PSO services. It also influences the requirements on the rolling stock, including the required capacity of vehicles or accessibility of the first-class places. The relationship between the carrier and passengers in terms of character of services is given by the demand for individual routes and the offer of the specific carrier, which can be oriented only for one type of services or both long-distance and regional PSO.
- Time period of the contract → In the relationship between contracting authority and carrier play an important role the stability of the contract. Railway undertaking is participating in the tender usually with a need to buy new vehicles and hire new employees for the operation of services under specific contract, which is suitable for the carrier only if the time period of the contract is longer. For the relationship between railway undertakings and passengers this represents a stable quality of services under one brand for a clearly defined longer time period (usually 10 years).
- Way of contracting PSO → in the relationship between contracting authority and railway undertaking determines the form of the negotiation process, which influences its duration and the transactional and administrative costs for both subjects. Between carrier and passengers plays a secondary role resulting in the quality of contracted services and system of regulated fares.
- Operational performance → in relationship between contracting authority and railway undertaking defines the range of services operated under specific contract and subsequently the need for the specified rolling stock and staff requirement, entering as well into the economically justified costs of railway undertaking and the final amount of compensation paid by the contracting authority. In the direction from carrier to passenger this indicator represents the offer of public transport services during different periods of day (week), influencing their travel decision.

- Compensation for PSO → represents a key efficiency indicator of every PSO contract. Contracting authorities usually make decision by the selection of railway undertaking for the contract taking into account the expected amount of compensation. For carriers participating in tenders, it means the need for the cost's optimization and detailed calculation of expected cost items related to the operation of services under specified contract. The main negotiations take a place between these two subjects and the resulting efficiency of services depends on how the decision was made. In the direction from carrier to passengers is the main effect of the agreed amount of compensation presented by the tariff conditions and regulated price of fares.
- Timetable requirements → Has an impact on the relationships between all three subjects and is closely related to the volume of operational performance. For the railway undertaking represents the need for effective vehicle and staff circulations, which also influence the costs and subsequently the amount of compensation. In the relation to passengers the optimal set of timetables can lead to more sustainable and usable public transport services, especially during the peak hours.
- Rolling stock requirements → Analogically as in the previous case, this indicator bring a huge impact on all mutual relationships on the market. Mainly in the field of the quality of services, where for the contracting authority represents the quality of PSO required from the railway undertaking to ensure that the contract will be sustainable for whole time period for each of the subjects. The carrier is providing the specific level of the quality of services, which motivate the passengers to use public transport.

Considering all these relationships and bonds, the creation of graphical model of the synergy effects between all subjects on the PSO market has been made, presented by the Figure 6. In the outer layer we can find external factors affected all main subjects on the PSO market. Gray darts between these subjects represent the financial flow, blue darts are expression of the flow of services. Boxes with indicators (circles) of PSO contracts linked to the subjects are expression of main mutual relationships (e.g., operational performance and revenue risk in relation to the contracting authority and railway undertaking providing PSO). Circles inside of the individual subjects are intended for labelling the in-house factors and flow of internal costs inside the organization (e.g. transactional costs). It is necessary to consider all indicators and market subjects together, because only this approach can lead to proper determination of their influence on each other and on the external subjects.

Figure 6: Final synergy model. Source: author

4. DISCUSSION

Looking at the previous results, we can consider the synergy model and determined relationships mainly in the countries implementing the system of awarding public services in transport same or similar to the EU legal framework. The UK franchise model, or fully deregulated rail passenger services in the US require different approach, or modification of the proposed in this paper. This is because of the character of public transport services in these countries, which are not fully subsidized by the central or local authority. We can find the main differences between these market models in the way how these services are supported by the state or belong fully or partially under the public sector, which is also reflected in the quality of services and rolling stock or timetable requirements. A question arises from this is, which model of railway market is the most efficient and should be implemented as the uniform approach of ordering and subsidising the public transport services. This is a complex issue, which required mixed approach, both quantitative and qualitative (e.g. panel of experts), and longer time period of the experience with individual market approaches.

Main limitations of this research consist in short experience of individual contracting authorities with organizing the public tenders for PSO in V4 countries, and therefore insufficient data sample needed for more complex approach. It is necessary to consider, that indicators entering the synergy model can vary in the future, which depends on current situation on the PSO market and first outcomes of the evaluation of the efficiency and success of public tenders from macro point of view. Synergy model proposed in this paper offers a complex insight into this problem from the perspective of all main subjects on the market with PSO and can be used as the first step for determining the main factors entering the PSO efficiency model. It can also help to set out and organize the main aspects of interest by interviewing the involved experts from railway market as a part of quantitative approach.

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